

CMS5 Analysis of the LDR Lite Benchmark: Initial Core at Hot Full Power with Equilibrium Xenon

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ABSTRACT

The Studsvik Core Management System (CMS5) is used to analyze the initial core of the Low-Temperature District Heating Reactor (LDR) Lite benchmark under hot full power conditions with equilibrium xenon. The LDR Lite benchmark was developed to support international code-to-code comparisons and is derived from the small modular reactor concept LDR-50, characterized by a thermal power output of 50 MW. High-fidelity reference solutions were generated using the Serpent 2 continuous-energy Monte Carlo code coupled with the subchannel thermal-hydraulic code SUBCHANFLOW.

Keywords: SMR, LDR, CASMO5, ENDF/B-VII.1, SIMULATE5

1. INTRODUCTION

CASMO5 [1] is an advanced lattice physics code for the generation of homogenized few-group data for downstream use by the advanced three-dimensional nodal simulator SIMULATE5 [2] within Studsvik's Core Management System (CMS5).

The CMS5 codes are applied to evaluate the initial core of the Low-Temperature District Heating Reactor (LDR) Lite benchmark [3]. The LDR Lite design is a public version of the LDR-50 design developed for international benchmarking. The LDR-50 is a 50 MW(t) integrated pressure water reactor with in-vessel control rod drives, boron-free operation, primary circuit driven by natural circulation, self-pressurization and passive decay heat removal through a dual vessel design. The design is classified as a Small Modular Reactor (SMR), [3].

The original LDR Lite benchmark included only a hot zero power exercise with two states: an all-rods-out cold state, where all control rod banks are fully withdrawn, and a critically rodded cold state with the regulating control rod banks inserted in a realistic configuration [4]. Recently, the benchmark was extended to include a hot full power (HFP) exercise featuring two states—zero and equilibrium xenon—and multiple configurations of the regulating control rod banks [3]. Reference solutions for the HFP state with equilibrium xenon are only available and were obtained from high-fidelity Monte Carlo simulations using the Serpent 2 code with the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library, coupled with the subchannel thermal-hydraulic code SUBCHANFLOW [3].

2. CMS5 OVERVIEW

CASMO5 [1] is a multigroup two-dimensional transport theory code for burnup calculations involving light water reactor assemblies or single pin cells. The code handles a geometry consisting of cylindrical fuel rods of varying composition in a square or triangular pitch array with allowance for boron,

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gadolinium or erbium-loaded fuel rods, burnable absorbers, cluster control rods, in-core instrument channels, and water gaps. Reflector and baffle calculations can also be performed with CASMO5.

The main characteristics of CASMO5 are as follows.

- Nuclear data for CASMO5 is collected in a library containing microscopic cross sections in 586 energy groups. Neutron energies in the range from 0 to 20 MeV are covered.
- A series of one-dimensional collision-probability micro-group calculations is performed for various pin types to obtain detailed neutron energy spectra used for cross-section condensation from the library group structure to the two-dimensional transport solver group structure.
- The two-dimensional transport solution is based upon the Method of Characteristics with a linear source approximation normally performed in 19 energy groups for uranium oxide fuel and 95 energy groups for reflectors.
- The neutron transport and depletion calculations are coupled via a predictor-corrector approach. This is particularly important when burnable absorber rods are involved. A special quadratic depletion model is used for lattices containing gadolinium. The burnup equations solver is based on the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method.

SIMULATE5 [2] is a three-dimensional multigroup nodal code for both square and hexagonal geometries. SIMULATE5 solves the multigroup diffusion equation. Cross sections are described by a hybrid microscopic-macroscopic model – more than 60 isotopes (17 actinides and 40+ fission products and burnable absorbers) are tracked.

Each assembly in the core is represented in detail with axial heterogeneities due to spacer grids, control rods, enrichment/burnable absorber zoning and staggered assembly heights treated explicitly. Radially, each quadrant of a pressurized water reactor (PWR) fuel assembly is divided into 5x5 heterogeneous radial submeshes. The pin powers/fluxes and the detector responses are computed based on the fine-scale solution obtained by the axial homogenization and radial submesh models.

The PWR thermal-hydraulics (TH) solver models the entire region between the lower and upper tie plates, explicitly representing each fuel assembly with an active channel and parallel bypass channels. For each axial node of a channel, the total mixture mass, steam mass, mixture enthalpy, and momentum balance equations are solved (a four-equation model). The three-dimensional fuel temperatures are computed by solving the radial Fourier heat conduction equation. Thermodynamic quantities are evaluated using the NIST/ASME steam/water function library.

3. LDR LITE BENCHMARK PROBLEM

The LDR lite reactor core [3] consists of 37 square fuel assemblies surrounded by a stainless-steel reflector (Figure 1). Each fuel assembly contains 264 fuel rods arranged in a 17x17 square lattice, with an active fuel length of 100 cm. The center position in each assembly is reserved for in-core instrumentation, while 24 additional positions are occupied by guide tubes. These guide tubes are connected to the top and bottom nozzles of the fuel assembly, providing structural support for the fuel grids. Three spacer grids are located at the bottom, middle, and top of the active fuel region: the bottom and middle spacers are made entirely of zircaloy, while the top spacer incorporates a stainless-steel sleeve with Inconel-718 inner egg-crates.

The fuel rods consist of low enriched uranium, in the form of cylindrical pellets of uranium dioxide (UO_2), enclosed in zircaloy cladding. Gadolinium, as gadolinium oxide (Gd_2O_3), is used as a burnable absorber mixed with uranium oxide in selected fuel assemblies. The core loading pattern is shown in Figure 2 comprising six fuel assembly types.

- Type 1: 1.50 wt% ^{235}U , 8 gadolinium rods (6.00 wt% Gd_2O_3).
- Type 2: 1.40 wt% ^{235}U .
- Type 3: 1.80 wt% ^{235}U , 4 gadolinium rods (6.00 wt% Gd_2O_3).
- Type 4: 2.40 wt% ^{235}U , 8 gadolinium rods (5.00 wt% Gd_2O_3).
- Type 5: 2.40 wt% ^{235}U , 8 gadolinium rods (9.00 wt% Gd_2O_3).
- Type 6: 1.80 wt% ^{235}U .

There are 37 rod cluster control actuators (RCCA), each driving 24 identical absorber rods. The absorber rods feature an Inconel-718 lower section and an enriched boron carbide upper section within stainless-steel cladding. The absorber section heights vary along the rods.

The RCCAs are organized into 4 regulating and 4 safety control banks (Figure 2), which are used to manage rapid reactivity changes and control the axial power distribution within the core.

Figure 1. LDR Benchmark – Core Radial (Left) and Core Axial (Right) Layout, [1]

Figure 2. LDR Benchmark – Core Loading Pattern (Left) & Control Rod Banks (Right), [1]

The HFP exercise of the LDR Lite benchmark comprises two states — zero and equilibrium xenon — each evaluated with different configurations of the control rod banks used for regulation [3]. The boundary conditions applied in the HFP exercise are summarized in Table I. Fuel behavior is modeled using fixed thermophysical properties, as provided in Table II, while the control rod bank configuration corresponding to the equilibrium xenon state is shown in Table III.

Reference solutions for the HFP state with equilibrium xenon are currently available. These were obtained from high-fidelity Monte Carlo simulations using the Serpent 2 code with the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library, coupled with the subchannel thermal-hydraulic code SUBCHANFLOW (SCF). Two coupling schemes were employed:

- Assembly-level coupling — one channel and representative fuel rod per assembly, with xenon treated at the assembly level, referred to as Serpent2-SCF (assembly);
- Subchannel-level coupling — a detailed subchannel and pin-level thermal-hydraulic and fuel behavior solution with xenon treated at the pin level, referred to as Serpent2-SCF (pin).

Table I. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise – Boundary Conditions.

Parameter	Value
Power	50 MW(t)
Core inlet mass flow rate*	237.12 kg/s
Core inlet temperature	379 K
Core outlet pressure	0.755 MPa

*Note: Uniformly distributed between all assemblies

Table II. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise – Fixed Thermophysical Properties for Fuel* and Cladding.

Parameter	Value
Fuel density	10.295 g/cm ³
Fuel thermal conductivity	5.2 W/(m·K)
Fuel specific heat capacity	290 J/(kg·K)
Cladding density	6.55 g/cm ³
Cladding thermal conductivity	14.7 W/(m·K)
Cladding specific heat capacity	310 J/(kg·K)
Gap conductance	5000 W/(m ² ·K)

*Note: Approximate values for fresh fuel with no gadolinium

Table III. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – Control Rod Bank Configuration

	Position, % withdrawn		Position, % withdrawn
Bank S1	100.0	Bank R2	33.0
Bank S4	100.0	Bank R3	36.0
Bank S7	100.0	Bank R5	34.0
Bank S8	100.0	Bank R6	44.0

4. MODELING OF LDR LITE BENCHMARK PROBLEM

Two-dimensional single-assembly calculations with CASMO5 were performed using zero net-current boundary conditions in octant assembly geometry for all axial variations of the fuel within the active core height. These variations include, for example, fuel regions with and without gadolinium burnable absorbers. The spacers located within the active fuel zone were modeled as an additional delta cross-section dependency, derived from CASMO5 branch calculations and incorporated into the library.

The radial reflector cross-section data were generated using the conventional one-dimensional reflector modeling approach, in which the reflector problem is solved directly with the two-dimensional transport code CASMO5. The single-assembly reflector option in CASMO5 allows explicit specification of reflector thickness and material compositions. CASMO5 performs a multi-group neutron transport calculation for a two-dimensional fuel assembly and adjacent one-dimensional reflector regions along one assembly edge, with a vacuum boundary condition applied on the outer reflector boundary. This modeling approach provides a high-order approximation of the neutron flux and leakage distribution at the fuel–reflector interface, as well as accurate reaction rate estimates within the radial reflector.

The reflector cross-sections were flux–volume weighted over the reflector region, and the corresponding boundary conditions were taken from the CASMO5 transport solution. Discontinuity factors for the homogenized reflector regions were defined as the ratios of heterogeneous to homogenized surface fluxes. For the LDR Lite problem, five distinct radial reflector models were developed using CASMO5, based on Figure 1. Each reflector model has a total thickness of 59.73726 cm, with the volume fractions of coolant and stainless steel, as well as the zone distances from the fuel interface, preserved according to the benchmark specifications. The gap between the fuel assembly and radial reflector was explicitly modeled.

The cross-sections for the axial (top and bottom) reflector regions were also generated from one-dimensional CASMO5 fuel–reflector calculations. The top and bottom reflector geometries represent the material compositions extending 18.719 cm above and 16.748 cm below the active fuel region.

CASMO5 calculations are performed using the default nuclear data library based on ENDF/B-VII.1.

The homogenized macroscopic and microscopic cross-sections, and the assembly discontinuity factors, are included in a few-group data library to be used by SIMULATE5. The library was generated in two-, four-, and eight-group energy structures. The CASMO5 single-assembly calculations assume zero-leakage boundary conditions and do not apply a critical buckling correction. In the reactor core, however, neutron in- and out-leakage modifies the local neutron spectrum, with higher-energy neutrons being more strongly affected due to their longer mean free paths. The four- and eight-group models, which include three and four epithermal-to-fast energy groups respectively, inherently capture leakage-induced spectral effects. When the two-group model is used, SIMULATE5 applies a fast-leakage correction model [5] to adjust the fast-group cross-sections and account for these spectral changes.

The three-dimensional core model for SIMULATE5 was developed as follows.

- Full core geometry (37 fuel assemblies and 32 radial reflector assemblies).
- Each assembly is modeled with 4 (2x2) radial and 9 axial nodes. Each quadrant is divided into 5 by 5 submeshes with the submesh option used.
- The neutronic effects of the spacer grids are modeled explicitly.
- HFP condition (Table I).
- The RCCAs are arranged in 8 control rod banks. The configuration is set according to Table II.
- ^{135}Xe concentration is set to equilibrium.
- The thermophysical properties of fuel and cladding are fixed (Table III).
- Standard TH calculation is performed.

5. RESULTS

The comparisons of effective multiplication factor (K_{eff}) between CMS5 and the reference solutions are summarized in Figure 3. The difference in K_{eff} ranges from –91 to 7 pcm relative to Serpent2-SCF (assembly) and from –31 to 67 pcm relative to Serpent2-SCF (pin). The variations in K_{eff} with different numbers of energy groups can be partially explained by differences in the fast-leakage treatment discussed in the previous section.

As the next step, the remaining portion of the exercise was analyzed, and results obtained with CMS5 using a four-group energy structure were found to offer the best compromise between accuracy and computational efficiency. These results were therefore selected for further evaluation in this study.

Figure 3. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – K_{eff} Comparison
(Legend: Bars – K_{eff} ; Markers – difference in K_{eff})

Comparisons of the radial and axial power distributions are presented in Figure 4 for Serpent2-SCF (assembly) and in Figure 5 for Serpent2-SCF (pin). Root mean square (RMS) in assembly power is 0.39 and 0.37 % respectively. Direct quantitative comparison in axial power cannot be performed because the axial nodalization differs from that used in the reference calculation.

Assembly	35	36	37
CMS5 in 4 groups	0.787	1.002	0.787
Serpent2/SCF (assembly)	0.783	1.008	0.783
Diff., %	0.46	-0.60	0.46

	30	31	32	33	34
	0.849	1.112	1.111	1.112	0.849
	0.844	1.116	1.113	1.116	0.844
	0.53	-0.38	-0.21	-0.38	0.53

	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
	0.787	1.112	1.112	1.111	1.112	1.112	0.787
	0.783	1.116	1.112	1.111	1.112	1.116	0.783
	0.46	-0.38	0.04	0.03	0.04	-0.38	0.46

	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	1.002	1.111	1.111	1.063	1.111	1.111	1.002
	1.008	1.113	1.111	1.061	1.111	1.113	1.008
	-0.60	-0.21	0.03	0.18	0.03	-0.21	-0.60

	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	0.787	1.112	1.112	1.111	1.112	1.112	0.787
	0.783	1.116	1.112	1.111	1.112	1.116	0.783
	0.46	-0.38	0.04	0.03	0.04	-0.38	0.46

	4	5	6	7	8
	0.849	1.112	1.111	1.112	0.849
	0.844	1.116	1.113	1.116	0.844
	0.53	-0.38	-0.21	-0.38	0.53

	1	2	3
	0.787	1.002	0.787
	0.783	1.008	0.783
	0.46	-0.60	0.46

Figure 4. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – Radial (Left) and Axial (Right) Power Comparison to Serpent2-SCF (assembly)

Accounting for the core symmetry, axially averaged pin-by-pin fission rate comparisons were performed in the octant core. The results are summarized in Table IV, with the RMS deviation in pin power ranging from 0.18 % for fuel assembly No 6 to 1.65 % for the peripheral fuel assembly No 2 relative to Serpent2-SCF (assembly), and from 0.18 % for fuel assembly No 6 to 1.04 % for the peripheral fuel assembly No 8 relative to Serpent2-SCF (pin). Detailed pin-by-pin fission rate comparisons for fuel assembly Nos 6 and 8 are presented in Figure 6 and Figure 7, where the color scale represents the range from the minimum to maximum difference within each individual fuel assembly.

Assembly		35	36	37		
CMS5 in 4 groups		0.787	1.002	0.787		
Serpent2/SCF (pin)		0.782	1.005	0.782		
Diff., %		0.54	-0.32	0.54		
	30	31	32	33	34	
	0.849	1.112	1.111	1.112	0.849	
	0.845	1.115	1.112	1.115	0.845	
	0.44	-0.28	-0.08	-0.28	0.44	
	23	24	25	26	27	28
	0.787	1.112	1.111	1.112	1.112	0.787
	0.782	1.115	1.114	1.114	1.115	0.782
	0.54	-0.28	-0.14	-0.32	-0.14	-0.28
	16	17	18	19	20	21
	1.002	1.111	1.111	1.063	1.111	1.002
	1.005	1.112	1.114	1.067	1.114	1.005
	-0.32	-0.08	-0.32	-0.35	-0.32	-0.08
	9	10	11	12	13	14
	0.787	1.112	1.111	1.111	1.112	0.787
	0.782	1.115	1.114	1.114	1.114	0.782
	0.54	-0.28	-0.14	-0.32	-0.14	-0.28
		4	5	6	7	8
		0.849	1.112	1.111	1.112	0.849
		0.845	1.115	1.112	1.115	0.845
		0.44	-0.28	-0.08	-0.28	0.44
		1	2	3		
		0.787	1.002	0.787		
		0.782	1.005	0.782		
		0.54	-0.32	0.54		

Figure 5. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – Radial (Left) and Axial (Right) Power Comparison to Serpent2-SCF (pin)

Table IV. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – Pin Powers Comparison

Assembly No	Serpent2/SCF (assembly)			Serpent2/SCF (pin)		
	MIN, %	MAX, %	RMS, %	MIN, %	MAX, %	RMS, %
2	-2.89	2.53	1.65	-1.99	1.80	0.94
3	-2.62	3.58	1.36	-3.02	2.76	0.96
6	-0.69	0.25	0.18	-0.53	0.37	0.18
7	-1.71	1.63	0.63	-2.10	0.95	0.54
8	-2.59	3.34	1.27	-3.20	2.86	1.04
12	-0.47	0.69	0.25	-0.78	0.34	0.26
13	-0.59	0.65	0.23	-0.71	0.67	0.26
19	-0.62	1.11	0.49	-1.47	0.74	0.66

Fuel Assembly No 6

Fuel Assembly No 8

Figure 6. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – Difference, % in Pin-by-Pin Fission Rate Compared to Serpent2-SCF (assembly) at Fuel Assembly Nos 6 (Left) and 8 (Right)

Fuel Assembly No 6

0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.2
0.4	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.4	
0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2		-0.2	-0.1		-0.3	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	
0.0	-0.1	-0.1		-0.4	-0.4	-0.1	0.0	-0.3	0.0	-0.1	-0.4	-0.4		-0.2	-0.1	0.0
0.2	-0.1	-0.4	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.4	-0.4	-0.1	0.2
-0.2	-0.4		-0.5	-0.3		-0.2	-0.1		-0.1	-0.2		-0.3	-0.5		-0.4	-0.2
0.1	-0.2	-0.4	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.4	-0.2	0.1
0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	0.1
0.2	-0.2		-0.3	-0.2		0.0	0.0		0.0	0.0		-0.2	-0.3		-0.2	0.2
0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.1
0.2	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-0.1	0.2
-0.1	-0.3		-0.5	-0.2		-0.1	-0.1		-0.1	-0.1		-0.2	-0.5		-0.3	-0.1
0.2	-0.2	-0.5	-0.5	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	-0.5	-0.5	-0.2	0.2
0.1	-0.2	0.0		-0.4	-0.4	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.4	-0.4		0.0	-0.2	0.1
0.1	0.0	0.3	0.1	-0.3		-0.2	-0.2		-0.2	-0.2		-0.3	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.1
0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.2
0.3	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.3

Fuel Assembly No 8

1.0	1.1	1.2	1.0	1.1	1.2	0.4	0.2	0.7	1.2	1.3	2.0	1.0	1.3	1.0	0.8	2.4
1.1	1.4	1.1	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.8	1.1	1.6	0.9	1.2	1.1	1.1	2.9
1.2	1.1	0.0	-0.4	0.5		-0.6	-0.7		0.5	1.2		0.4	1.0	1.0	0.7	1.6
0.9	0.7	-0.4		0.3	-0.2	-0.9	-1.0	-0.4	0.0	0.9	1.9	0.8		0.7	0.3	1.4
1.1	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.3	-1.1	-0.6	-0.6	-0.1	0.4	-0.3	0.9	-0.2	-1.5	-0.1	0.6	2.1
1.2	0.7		-0.2	-1.1		-1.1	-1.4		0.8	0.5		-2.1	-3.2		-0.5	0.0
0.4	0.2	-0.6	-0.9	-0.6	-1.1	-1.5	-1.4	-0.4	0.4	-0.1	-1.7	-0.5	-1.0	-0.4	0.7	1.8
0.2	0.0	-0.7	-1.0	-0.6	-1.4	-1.4	-1.4	-1.0	-0.3	-0.8	-1.4	-1.0	-0.1	0.0	0.7	1.7
0.7	0.3		-0.4	-0.1		-0.4	-1.0		0.0	-0.1		-0.6	0.2		0.9	2.2
1.2	0.8	0.5	0.0	0.4	0.8	0.4	-0.3	0.0	0.6	1.0	0.4	-0.2	0.7	0.9	0.9	1.7
1.3	1.1	1.2	0.9	-0.3	0.5	-0.1	-0.8	-0.1	1.0	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	0.6	1.1	1.3	1.9
2.0	1.6		1.9	0.9		-1.7	-1.4		0.4	-0.3		-0.2	-1.0		0.4	0.4
1.0	0.9	0.4	0.8	-0.2	-2.1	-0.5	-1.0	-0.6	-0.2	-0.3	-0.2	-0.8	-0.8	-0.2	0.9	1.5
1.3	1.2	1.0		-1.5	-3.2	-1.0	0.0	0.2	0.8	0.6	-0.9	-0.8		2.3	1.3	1.8
1.0	1.1	1.0	0.7	-0.1		-0.4	0.1		1.0	1.2		-0.1	2.3	2.1	1.4	1.7
0.8	1.1	0.7	0.3	0.6	-0.5	0.7	0.7	1.0	1.0	1.4	0.5	1.0	1.3	1.4	1.6	2.1
2.4	2.9	1.6	1.4	2.1	0.0	1.8	1.8	2.3	1.9	2.1	0.7	1.7	1.8	1.6	2.1	2.2

Figure 7. LDR Lite Benchmark, HFP Exercise, Xenon Equilibrium State – Difference, % in Pin-by-Pin Fission Rate Compared to Serpent2-SCF (pin) at Fuel Assembly Nos 6 (Left) and 8 (Right)

6. CONCLUSIONS

The LDR Lite initial core under hot full power conditions with equilibrium xenon was evaluated using the CMS5 code system with two-, four-, and eight-group energy structures. Excellent agreement was achieved with high-fidelity reference solutions obtained from the Serpent 2 code coupled at the assembly and subchannel levels with the SUBCHANFLOW code. This study presented detailed comparisons for the CMS5 four-group energy structure, including the effective multiplication factor (K_{eff}) and assembly- and pin-level power distributions, demonstrating an optimal balance between predictive accuracy and computational efficiency.

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